

Some New Benzimidazolylalkyl Thioureas and Thiazolidones as Possible Anticonvulsants

M. I. HUSAIN* and G. C. SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow-226 007

and

P. R. DUA

Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow-226 001

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Thirty new N^1 -(2-benzimidazolylalkyl)- N^8 -aryl thioureas and their corresponding 2-arylimino-3-(2-benzimidazolylalkyl)thiazolidones obtained by the cyclisation of the former were synthesised. Some of these compounds were screened for anticonvulsant activity in mice at $1/5$ ALD_{50} dose level against supramaximal electroshock and pentylenetetrazole induced seizures. Excepting N^1 -(2-benzimidazolyl propyl)- N^8 -*p*-methoxyphenyl thiourea which afforded 40% protection against pentylenetetrazole induced seizures, the compounds were found to be inactive.

SEVERAL thiourea derivatives¹⁻³ have been reported to exhibit pronounced anticonvulsant activity. Thiazolidones are also known to possess diverse biological properties like hypnotic⁴, local anaesthetic⁵ and anticonvulsant^{6,7}. Some 2-arylimino-3-(3,4-dimethoxy phenethyl)thiazolidones⁸ have recently been reported to display good anticonvulsant activity. Further, a few benzimidazole derivatives^{9,10} have been found to possess CNS depressant and anticonvulsant activities. Stimulated by these observations, the authors synthesised the title compounds as per Scheme 1 with the hope that

these might display a high order of anticonvulsant activity.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected.

2-(Aminoalkyl)benzimidazoles: These were synthesised by the method of Cescon and Day¹¹. The four 2-(aminoalkyl) benzimidazoles thus obtained are (i) 2-(aminomethyl)benzimidazole, m.p. = 250° (lit¹², m.p. = 248°); (ii) 2-(α -methylaminomethyl)benzimidazole, m.p. = 185° (lit¹², m.p. = 195°); (iii) 2-(aminoethyl)benzimidazole, m.p. = 159° (lit¹², m.p. = 161°) and (iv) 2-(aminopropyl)benzimidazole, m.p. = 110° (Found: N, 24.48. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{13}N_3$; N, 24.00%).

N^1 -(2-Benzimidazolylalkyl)- N^8 -aryl thioureas: 2-(Aminoalkyl)benzimidazole (0.02 mole) and an aryl isothiocyanate (0.02 mole) were mixed in anhydrous benzene (30 ml) and the mixture refluxed on a steam bath for 1-2 hr. Benzene was distilled off under reduced pressure and a solid mass separated out on cooling. It was filtered, washed with water and ether and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

2-Arylimino-3-(2-benzimidazolylalkyl)thiazolid-4-ones: N^1 -(2-Benzimidazolylalkyl)- N^8 -arylthiourea (0.01 mole), chloroacetic acid (0.01 mole), anhydrous sodium acetate (0.015 mole) and glacial acetic acid (15 ml) were refluxed for 5-8 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice with stirring and kept overnight in a refrigerator. The solid thus separated was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 2).

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—N¹-(2-BENZIMIDAZOLYLALKYL)-N²-ARYL THIOUREAS

Sl.No.	X	R ¹	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Nitrogen %	
						Found	Calcd.
1*	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ O	>300	55	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ OS	16.78	16.47
2	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -Cl	195	56	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ SCl	16.58	16.94
3	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	H	200	59	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ S	18.56	18.06
4*	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	178-80	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₄ S	17.92	16.94
5	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>m</i> -Cl	180	50	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ SCl	16.74	18.06
6	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	180	52	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₄ S	17.78	17.69
7*	-CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -Cl	195	51	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ SCl	17.28	17.12
8*	-CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ O	175	58	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₄ OS	17.48	18.91
9	-CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	187-88	53	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ S	18.65	18.91
10	-CH ₂ -	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	173-74	55	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ S	18.78	17.69
11	-CH ₂ -	<i>m</i> -Cl	195-6	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ SCl	17.42	19.85
12	-CH ₂ -	H	170-72	50	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ S	19.56	15.51
13*	-CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -Br	189-90	55	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ SBr	15.05	14.93
14	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -Br	145	54	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ SBr	14.68	16.25
15 ^b	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -Cl	170-72	58	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₄ SCl	16.55	15.81
16	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ - CH ₃	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ O	140	50	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ OS	15.67	
17	-CH-	<i>p</i> -Cl	260	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ SCl	16.45	16.94
18	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	H	180	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₄ S	18.48	18.06
19*	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ - CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	160	55	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₄ S	17.63	17.94
20**	-CH- CH ₃	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ O	195-6	53	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ OS	16.85	16.47
21*	-CH- CH ₃	H	193-94	50	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ S	18.45	18.91
22*	-CH- CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	203-04	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₄ S	18.38	18.06
23*	-CH- CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Br	198	55	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ SBr	14.48	14.93
24	-CH-	<i>m</i> -Cl	190	57	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ SCl	16.48	16.94
25 ^d	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -Br	192-93	51	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₄ SBr	14.77	14.39
26*	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>m</i> -Cl	180	53	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₄ SCl	16.70	16.25
27*	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ - CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	154	55	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ OS	16.75	16.47
28*	-CH-	<i>p</i> CH ₃ O	180	59	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ OS	17.48	17.17
29	-CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	250	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ OS	17.57	17.94
30	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	260	53	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₄ OS	17.45	17.17

- a. Found: C, 62.78; H, 5.35. Calcd.; C, 62.38, H, 5.81%.
 b. Found: C, 59.67; H, 4.48. Calcd.; C, 59.21; H, 4.93%.
 c. Found: C, 63.35; H, 5.62. Calcd.; C, 63.52; H, 5.88%.
 d. Found: C, 52.85; H, 4.76. Calcd.; C, 52.44; H, 4.37%.

* Screened for anticonvulsant activity.

TABLE 2—2-ARYLIMINO-3-(2-BENZIMIDAZOLYLALKYL)THIAZOLID-4-ONES⁺⁺

Sl. No.	X	R ¹	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Nitrogen %	
						Found	Calcd.
1*	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ O	240	55	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ S	14.55	14.73
2	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -Cl	185	56	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	15.58	15.11
3	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	H	270	57	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S	16.25	16.66
4*	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	190	58	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₂ S	16.42	16.00
5	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>m</i> -Cl	99	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	15.47	15.11
6*	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	250	55	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₂ S	16.35	16.00
7*	-CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -Cl	153	56	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	15.28	15.70
8 ^b	-CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ O	140	59	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₂ S	15.55	15.30
9	-CH ₂ -	<i>m</i> -Cl	140	58	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	15.38	15.70
10	-CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	190	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₂ S	16.27	16.66
11	-CH ₂ -	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	130	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S	16.20	16.66
12	-CH ₂ -	H	178-80	55	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S	17.79	17.39
13*	-CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -Br	180	57	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ SBr	13.56	13.96
14*	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -Br	120	58	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ SBr	13.86	13.49
15	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -Cl	125	59	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	14.78	14.56

(Table 2 Contd.)

16 ^c	$\begin{array}{c} -\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2- \\ \\ \text{OH} \end{array}$	<i>p</i> -C ₂ H ₅ O	90	60	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	14.65	14.21
17	-CH-	<i>p</i> -Cl	192-94	55	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₄ OSCl	15.65	15.11
18*	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	H	160	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₄ OS	15.76	16.00
19*	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ - CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	203-4	58	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ OS	15.76	15.38
20 ^d	-CH- CH ₂	<i>p</i> -C ₂ H ₅ O	226-27	59	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ S	14.29	14.73
21*	-CH- CH ₃	H	203-4	55	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₄ OS	16.88	16.66
22*	-CH- CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	232-33	56	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₄ OS	16.45	16.00
23*	-CH- CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Br	165	59	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ OSBr	13.39	13.49
24	-CH-	<i>m</i> -Cl	214-15	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ OSCl	15.45	15.11
25*	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -Br	238-40	55	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ OSBr	13.48	13.02
26 ^e *	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>m</i> -Cl	130	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ OSCl	14.75	14.52
27*	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ - CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	100	57	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ OS	15.66	15.38
28*	-CH-	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	242	59	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S	15.70	15.30
29	-CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	210	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S	15.57	15.90
30	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	260	55	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S	15.68	15.30

⁺⁺ Showed ir bands at 3400 cm⁻¹ (-NH str.), 2950 cm⁻¹ (C-H str.), 1730 cm⁻¹ (CO of sec. amide), 1640 cm⁻¹ (C=N str.), 1600 cm⁻¹ (C-C str. aromatic).

- Found: C, 65.39; H, 5.35. Calcd.: C, 65.14; H, 5.14%.
- Found: C, 62.56; H, 4.57. Calcd.: C, 62.29; H, 4.91%.
- Found: C, 63.45; H, 5.50. Calcd.: C, 63.95; H, 5.58%.
- Found: C, 63.63; H, 5.48. Calcd.: C, 63.15; H, 5.26%.
- Found: C, 59.39; H, 4.75. Calcd.: C, 59.14; H, 4.66%.

* Screened for anticonvulsant activity.

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